

Interaction of deoxyribonucleic acid with H₁ histone in the unirradiated and gamma irradiated states *in vitro**

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This study was undertaken in order to find out the effect of solvent composition on mode of interaction of H₁ histone with DNA, suitability of DNA, H₁ histone and DNA-H₁ complex as *in vitro* biological dosimeters and protection possibility of DNA by H₁ histone against ionizing radiation-induced damage. Analytical techniques were used for the study of complex formation. Gamma irradiation was used to deliver doses to the biopolymers and their complexes. Equilibrium dialysis method was used for complex formation. FBX dosimetry was done for the delivery of total dose and dose rate determination. DNA : H₁ complex formation ratio were : 4.17×10^{-9} : 4.652×10^{-6} ML⁻¹ in 10^{-3} M phosphate buffer; 4.17×10^{-9} : 1.163×10^{-6} ML⁻¹ in 0.1 M phosphate buffer and 2.085×10^{-9} : 9.304×10^{-7} ML⁻¹ in 0.15 M SSC buffer.

Linearity in response with absorbed dose up to 50 Gy (dose rate 1.50 Gy/min) was observed with (i) DNA at 207 nm and 259 nm at 4.17×10^{-9} ML⁻¹, (ii) with H₁ histone at 202 nm and 270 nm at 1.163×10^{-6} ML⁻¹ in 0.1 M phosphate buffer, pH 7.0, (iii) with DNA : H₁ at 206 nm and 260 nm in 0.1 M phosphate buffer, (iv) with DNA : H₁ at 226 nm and 260 nm in SSC buffer. A constant decrease in fluorescent intensity (Ex 280 nm, Em 338 nm) was observed for H₁ histone with increase in dose. The average percentage hyperchromicity in 0.1 M phosphate buffer was 20% for DNA, 11% for H₁ histone and 17% for DNA : H₁ complex. In 0.15 M SSC buffer, for the complex it was 14% for a dose of 50 Gy at a dose rate of 1.5 Gy/min. The degrees of unfolding of the chromophores for this complex with dose were different in different solvents.

Complex formations are due to electrostatic, minor groove binding and intercalation modes and are solvent dependent. DNA, H₁ and DNA : H₁ complex can be used as *in vitro* biological dosimeters. Binding modes are responsible for protection of DNA by H₁ histone up to a dose of 50 Gy.

H₁ histone (M.W. 21,500, lysine/arginine 20.0), number of amino-acid residues 215, specific positive charge 0.24) occurs in the nucleosome as a linker and links the linker DNA^{1,2}. It occurs as a monomer per nucleosome and it helps the nucleosome moiety to remain intact. It consists of a short terminal tail of about 80 amino-acids and a highly positively charged C-terminal tail, which contains approximately 100 amino-acids. Because of this stereospecific position it is susceptible to radiation dose. Moreover, as it occurs in a complex form with DNA it does not allow radiation-induced changes to be permeated to DNA. Reconstituted H₁-DNA complex prepared under physiological condition simulates chromatin like structure³⁻⁵. Both H₁ and DNA retain their ordered structures in 0.1 M phosphate buffer and 0.15 M SSC buffer⁶. Recently, 10^{-3} M phosphate buffer has been used to understand DNA-Hoechst interaction⁷. So, all these three solvents have been used in our study. Though preliminary studies have been done on

dose-response relationship for H₁ histone^{8,9} and DNA¹⁰, we undertook a slightly detailed study for these two biopolymers and their complex. So, the objectives of our study were : (i) to find out mode of interaction of H₁ histone with DNA in different solvents, (ii) suitability of these biopolymers and their complexes as *in vitro* biological dosimeters and (iii) possibility of protection of DNA against ionizing radiation by H₁ histone.

Results

It is known that DNA follows Lambert Beer's law up to 100 µg/ml in 10^{-3} M and 0.1 M phosphate buffer and 0.15 M SSC buffer^{11,12}. H₁ histone in 10^{-3} M phosphate buffer and 0.1 M phosphate buffer followed Lambert Beer's law up to 100 µg/ml at 270 nm and 210–230 nm⁸. The isoelectric point of whole histone has been reported by us to be 11.20¹³.

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Table 1. Interaction of H₁ histone with DNA as determined by analytical methods

Solvent 0.1 M phosphate buffer, pH 7.0				
Biopolymer (ML ⁻¹)	$\lambda_{\max}$ (nm)	$A_{\lambda_{\max}}$	Fluorescent intensity Ex 287 nm; Em 305 nm	Conductance at 1000 Hz (μMho)
DNA 4.17 × 10 ⁻⁹	207, 260	0.94 ± 0.005	0.41 ± 0.005	2100 ± 25
H ₁ 1.163 × 10 ⁻⁶	205, 270	0.78 ± 0.005	0.47 ± 0.005	1800 ± 20
DNA 4.17 × 10 ⁻⁹ + H ₁ 1.163 × 10 ⁻⁶	206, 255-260	1.02 ± 0.010 0.63 ± 0.005	0.26 ± 0.010	1600 ± 50

n = 3.

DNA, in 0.1 M phosphate buffer (pH 7.0), when irradiated to increasing doses up to 50 Gy did not show variation in the position of absorption maximum. Linearity in absorbance intensity at 207 nm and 259 nm up to a dose of 50 Gy were observed (Fig. 1). Percentage hyperchromicity at 207 nm and 259 nm were 20% and 18% respectively at 50 Gy for a dose rate of 1.5 Gy/min. The average $A_{207 \text{ nm}}/\text{Gy}$ and $A_{259 \text{ nm}}/\text{Gy}$ values were found to be 0.0031 and 0.0022 respectively. These are the slopes of these two lines (Fig. 1).

Fig. 1. Absorbance values of deoxyribonucleic acid at 207 nm and 259 nm as a function of dose of gamma irradiation. Concentration of DNA 4.17 × 10⁻⁹ ML⁻¹, solvent 0.1 M phosphate buffer, dose rate 1.50 Gy/min, pH 7.0 : (■) A_{207 nm}; (●) A_{259 nm}.

H₁ histone in 0.1 M phosphate buffer showed linear increase at $A_{202 \text{ nm}}$ and $A_{270 \text{ nm}}$ with dose up to 70 Gy. No change in position of absorption maximum took place. Percentage hyperchromicity at 202 nm and 270 nm were 11% and 126% respectively. The average $A_{202 \text{ nm}}/\text{Gy}$ and $A_{270 \text{ nm}}/\text{Gy}$ values were found to be 0.0024 and 0.0042 respectively. These are the slopes of these two lines (Fig. 2). Nucleohistone also followed Lambert Beer's law up to 75 μg/ml in the unirradiated state and absorption values of X-peak (i.e. at 260 nm) and Y-peak (i.e. at 205 nm) increased with dose¹⁴.

In 0.1 M phosphate buffer, pH 7.00, when to a fixed concentration of DNA (4.17 × 10⁻⁹ ML⁻¹) increasing concentration of H₁ histone was mixed, it was found that at a

Fig. 2. Absorbance values of H₁ histone at 202 nm and 270 nm as a function of dose of gamma irradiation. Concentration 1.163 × 10⁻⁶ ML⁻¹, solvent 0.1 M phosphate buffer, dose rate 1.50 Gy/min, pH 7.0 : (■) A_{202 nm}; (●) A_{270 nm}.

concentration ratio of 4.17 × 10⁻⁹ : 1.163 × 10⁻⁶ ML⁻¹ of DNA : H₁ complex formation occurred (Table 1).

The evidences of complex formation are : (1) broadening of X-peak of the complex compared to sharp peaks for constituents (complex 255-260 nm, DNA 260 nm and H₁ histone 270 nm), (ii) decrease in absorbance intensity at $A_{255 \text{ nm}-260 \text{ nm}}$ for complex compared to $A_{260 \text{ nm}}$ for DNA, (iii) conductance value of complex was much less than the additive values of the constituents and (iv) quenching of fluorescence.

In 0.15 M SSC buffer, pH 7.00, at a concentration ratio of 2.085 × 10⁻⁹ ML⁻¹ of DNA with 9.304 × 10⁻⁷ ML⁻¹ of H₁ histone complex formation occurred. The evidences are as follows : (i) broadening of the X-peak of the complex was observed compared to sharp peaks for constituents (complex 259-265 nm, DNA 260 nm and H₁ 270 nm), (ii) reaching of saturation of absorbance intensity at absorption maximum (i.e. 0.58), (iii) quenching of fluorescence intensity for complex (i.e. 0.57 for DNA, 0.38 for H₁ histone and 0.10 for DNA : H₁ complex) and (iv) decrease of conductance value for complex compared to additive values for constituents (i.e. DNA 7000 μMho, H₁ 6600 μMho and DNA : H₁ 6400 μMho) (Table 2).

Table 2. Interaction of H₁ histone with DNA as determined by analytical methods

Solvent 0.15 M standard saline citrate, pH 7.0				
Biopolymer (ML ⁻¹)	$\lambda_{\max}$ (nm)	$A_{\lambda_{\max}}$	Fluorescent intensity Ex 287 nm; Em 305 nm	Conductance at 1000 Hz (μMho)
DNA 2.085 × 10 ⁻⁹	260	0.39 ± 0.005	0.57 ± 0.005	7000 ± 50
H ₁ 9.304 × 10 ⁻⁷	270	0.08 ± 0.001	0.38 ± 0.007	6600 ± 75
DNA 2.085 × 10 ⁻⁹ + H ₁ 9.304 × 10 ⁻⁷	259-265	0.58 ± 0.005	0.10 ± 0.002	6400 ± 50

n = 3.

In 10⁻³ M phosphate buffer, pH 7.0, H₁ histone showed an absorption maximum at 205 nm and 270 nm at a concentration of 2.32 × 10⁻⁶ ML⁻¹. The $A_{205 \text{ nm}}$ and $A_{270 \text{ nm}}$ values were 0.850 and 0.175 respectively. DNA showed an absorption maximum at 260 nm at a concentration of 8.34 ×

10^{-9} ML^{-1} . The $A_{260 \text{ nm}}$ value was 0.750. But, when to $4.17 \times 10^{-9} \text{ ML}^{-1}$ of DNA increasing concentration of H_1 histone were mixed, a broad plateau (i.e. 250–270 nm) was obtained. The absorbances in this wavelength range increased with increase in concentration of H_1 histone.

Table 3. Fluorescent intensity of H_1 histone as a function of dose
Solvent 10^{-3} M phosphate buffer, dose rate 0.009 Gy/s. Concentration of H_1 histone $3.326 \times 10^{-6} \text{ ML}^{-1}$. Slit width 0.5 nm. Ex 280 nm; Em 338 nm

Dose (Gy)	Fluorescent intensity count
Unirradiated	460 ± 10
25	350 ± 20
50	290 ± 10
75	240 ± 10
100	190 ± 20

n = 3.

The different absorbance characteristics in Fig.3 indicated as (i) to (v) are given below : (i) DNA ($8.34 \times 10^{-9} \text{ ML}^{-1}$), $\lambda_{\text{max}} = 260 \text{ nm}$, $A_{260 \text{ nm}} = 0.75$, (ii) DNA : H_1 $4.17 \times 10^{-9} : 4.652 \times 10^{-6} \text{ ML}^{-1}$, $A_{270 \text{ nm}} = 0.275$, (iii) DNA : H_1 $4.17 \times 10^{-9} : 3.489 \times 10^{-6} \text{ ML}^{-1}$, $A_{270 \text{ nm}} = 0.225$, (iv) DNA : H_1 $4.17 \times 10^{-9} : 2.326 \times 10^{-6} \text{ ML}^{-1}$, $A_{270 \text{ nm}} = 0.20$, (v) H_1 ($2.326 \times 10^{-6} \text{ ML}^{-1}$), $\lambda_{\text{max}1} = 205 \text{ nm}$ and $\lambda_{\text{max}2} = 270 \text{ nm}$, $A_{205 \text{ nm}} = 0.85$ and $A_{270 \text{ nm}} = 0.175$ (Fig. 3).

Fig. 3. UV absorption spectra of DNA, H_1 histone and their combinations in different proportions. Solvent 10^{-3} M phosphate buffer, pH 7.0 : (♦) DNA $8.34 \times 10^{-9} \text{ ML}^{-1}$; (■) DNA : H_1 $4.17 \times 10^{-9} : 4.652 \times 10^{-6} \text{ ML}^{-1}$; (▲) DNA : H_1 $4.17 \times 10^{-9} : 3.489 \times 10^{-6} \text{ ML}^{-1}$; (X) DNA H_1 $4.17 \times 10^{-9} : 2.326 \times 10^{-6} \text{ ML}^{-1}$; (O) H_1 histone $2.326 \times 10^{-6} \text{ ML}^{-1}$.

The fluorescent intensity of H_1 histone in 10^{-3} M phosphate buffer at pH 7.0 decreased consistently with increasing radiation dose at a dose rate of 0.009 Gy/s up to 100 Gy by 60% (Ex 280 nm; Em 338 nm) (Table 3).

The $A_{206 \text{ nm}}$ and $A_{260 \text{ nm}}$ values increased linearly with dose up to 50 Gy in 0.1 M phosphate buffer for DNA : H_1 complex. Similarly $A_{226 \text{ nm}}$ values and $A_{260 \text{ nm}}$ values also increased with dose linearly up to 50 Gy in 0.15 M SSC buffer for DNA : H_1 complex. Percentage hyperchromicity was 18% at 206 nm and 260 nm in 0.1 M phosphate buffer but that in 0.15 M SSC buffer the values were 20% at 226

nm and 18% at 260 nm for the same dose. The average $A_{206 \text{ nm}}/\text{Gy}$ and $A_{260 \text{ nm}}/\text{Gy}$ in 0.1 M phosphate buffer were found to be 0.0042 and 0.0013 respectively. Similarly average $A_{226 \text{ nm}}/\text{Gy}$ and $A_{260 \text{ nm}}/\text{Gy}$ in 0.15 M SSC buffer were found to be 0.0024 and 0.0020 respectively. These are the slopes of these four lines (Fig. 4).

Fig. 4. Dose-response relationship of DNA : H_1 complex in 0.1 M phosphate buffer, pH 7.0, dose rate 1.50 Gy/min. ratio of DNA : $\text{H}_1 = 4.17 \times 10^{-9} : 1.163 \times 10^{-6} \text{ ML}^{-1}$: (O) $A_{206 \text{ nm}}$; (●) $A_{260 \text{ nm}}$. Dose response relationship of DNA : H_1 complex in 0.15 M SSC buffer, pH 7.0, dose rate 1.50 Gy/min, ratio of DNA : $\text{H}_1 = 2.085 \times 10^{-9} : 9.304 \times 10^{-7} \text{ ML}^{-1}$: (Δ) $A_{226 \text{ nm}}$; (▲) $A_{260 \text{ nm}}$.

Discussion

Linearity in dose response relationship at 207 nm and 259 nm up to 50 Gy for DNA is due to exposition of $-\text{C}=\text{C}-\text{C}=\text{O}$ and $-\text{C}=\text{C}-\text{C}=\text{N}-$ chromophores proportionally with dose¹¹. The first one is due to breakage of phosphodiester bond and the second one is due to breakage of hydrogen bond between the bases. The Y-peak transitions are more sensitive compared to X-peak¹². But in this solvent and within the dose range drastic transition leading to complete transition from helix to coil did not take place. As the solvent contains sufficient amount of counterions (e.g. Na^+ , PO_4^{3-}) these will adhere to the double helix preventing the radiation-induced transition of DNA from helix to gel bead^{13,14} (Fig. 1).

Similarly, linearity in dose-response relationship at 202 nm and 270 nm for H_1 histone can be ascribed as due to proportional increase in imidazole group of histidine¹⁵ (up to 205 nm) and tyrosine, tryptophan, phenylalanine and histidine (270–280 nm) (Fig. 2).

DNA formed a complex with H_1 histone in the concentration ratio of $4.17 \times 10^{-9} \text{ ML}^{-1} : 1.163 \times 10^{-6} \text{ ML}^{-1}$ in 0.1 M phosphate buffer. The broadness of the absorption peak of the complex is a clear indication of slow addition of H_1 histone to the binding sites of DNA. This charge neutralization complex has been formed by interaction of phosphate groups of DNA and different basic amino-acids like arginine > histidine > lysine whose hydrophilicity has been shown in decreasing order¹⁶. But, it may not be a saturated

complex where all the binding sites of DNA in 4.17×10^{-9} ML⁻¹ are filled up by 1.163×10^{-6} ML⁻¹ of H₁ histone (Table 1). That DNA forms a complex with H₁ histone in sodium chloride solvent prepared by gradient dialysis has been evidenced by melting profile studies reported earlier¹⁷. The T_{m.1} and T_{m.2} values were reported as 50–55°C and 76°C respectively.

In SSC solvent the concentration ratio of complex formation is 2.085×10^{-9} ML⁻¹ of DNA with 9.304×10^{-7} ML⁻¹ of H₁ histone. This charge neutralization complex is due to interaction between arginine > histidine > lysine with phosphate groups. The hydrophilicity of the amino-acids will be altered due to the counterions like Na⁺ and Cl⁻ ions. The counterions will also bind per se with the phosphate groups of DNA (Table 2).

In 10⁻³ M phosphate buffer also complex formation has occurred in the concentration ratio of 4.17×10^{-9} ML⁻¹ of DNA : 4.652×10^{-6} ML⁻¹ of H₁ histone (Fig. 3). The value of the equilibrium constant has been found to be 1.19 ML⁻¹.

The broadness of the plateau in all the three solvents (λ_{max} 255–260 nm in 0.1 M phosphate buffer, λ_{max} 259–265 nm in 0.15 M SSC buffer and 255–266 nm in 10⁻³ M phosphate buffer) are clear indications of loose nature of binding in the ground state of the complex. The characteristic absorption peak for charge transfer complexes of this type becomes broad¹⁵. The variations in position of λ_{max} for different solvents are due to variation in polarity of the solvents¹⁸ and variation in refractive index of the solvents¹⁹. It is expected that in all these solvents the positively charged amino-acids must have bound with phosphate groups with almost same order²⁰ of association constants. Moreover, it appears to be co-operative binding in all the solvents as the solvent molarity, size of DNA and A-T content are favourable for it. H₁ histone probably binds in the minor groove²¹ (Fig. 3). The end to end distance and compaction volume for H₁ histone obtained from chicken has been reported to be 720 Å and 10395 (Å)³ respectively²².

As the average percentage hyperchromicity in both 0.1 M phosphate buffer and 0.15 M SSC buffer was 18–20% for DNA : H₁ complex it may be inferred that packing of DNA by H₁ histone was stereospecific through the chromophores of DNA and H₁ histone. Configuration of H₁ histone allows it to bind to DNA by minor groove binding and intercalation. Radiation induced unfolding of chromophores (e.g. imidazole group of histidine – A_{206 nm}, peptide bonds – A_{226 nm} and -C=C-C=N- A_{260 nm}) took place very feebly because of compaction²². The slopes mentioned in results section of Fig. 4 indicate the degree of increasing unfolding per Gy of the chromophores with dose.

DNA, H₁ histone and DNA : H₁ complex have shown

linear increase in absorbance intensity with increase in dose up to 50 Gy at a dose rate of 1.50 Gy/min. Radiation-induced increase in absorbance values at 207 nm and 259 nm with dose for DNA, at 202 nm and 270 nm with dose for H₁ histone and at 206 nm, 226 nm and 260 nm with dose for DNA : H₁ complex were found to be linear in the respective solvents (Figs. 1, 2 and 4). The values were found to be reproducible for five days. So, these can be used as *in vitro* biological dosimeters up to 50 Gy in the respective solvents.

As a result of irradiation decrease in fluorescent intensity for H₁ histone occurs. This is due to scission of some of the fluorophors of H₁ histone like tyrosine. It has been reported that hydrated electrons react with proteins and induce deamination, even for H₁ histone, thereby leading to main chain scission²³. This can also be due to radiation-induced alteration in the configuration of H₁ histone leading to positioning of the fluorophors inside the core and their inaccessibility to excitation²⁴ (Table 3).

Conclusion :

DNA, H₁ histone and DNA-H₁ complex can be used as biological dosimeters *in vitro* up to 50 Gy at a dose rate of 1.5 Gy/min. In all the experimental solvents DNA formed a complex with H₁ histone in the concentration ratios indicated. By thus binding H₁ histone has offered protection to DNA against gamma radiation-induced damage up to 50 Gy.

Experimental

Calf thymus DNA (Lot No. D1501), Mol. Wt. 6.0×10^6 and histone H₁ (Lot No. 59C, 8051, H8861, M.W. 21,500) were obtained from Sigma Chemical Company. Sodium chloride, sodium phosphate, sodium citrate, hydrochloric acid, sodium hydroxide etc. were of analytical grade. Double distilled water was used. Instrumental measurements were done as given below :

UV visible spectra – GBC 916 (Australia), fluorescence measurements – spectrophotofluorimeter (Model FS 900, CDT, Edinburg, UK), analytical instruments with a slit width of 0.5 mm. pH measurements were done in Toshniwal pH meter (Model CL 46), India. Conductance measurements were done in conductivity bridge (Elico, Model CM 82T), India. Irradiations were done in Gamma Cell 220, Atomic Energy of Canada (Model GC 220). Calf thymus DNA was allowed to swell in 0.10 M and 10⁻³ M phosphate buffer, pH 7 and 0.15 M standard saline citrate, pH 7.0. Three stock solutions of DNA of concentration 400 µg/ml were prepared in these solvents by swelling and subsequently thoroughly stirred by a magnetic stirrer over-

night. Similarly stock solutions of H₁ histone were prepared (concentration 400 µg/ml) in these solvents, but swelling was not necessary. Requisite concentration of each biopolymer was prepared by suitable dilution with a desired solvent. Histone-DNA interaction was done by gradient dialysis method in these three solvents by a method as reported earlier²⁵. Gamma irradiations of solutions were done in glass tubes of uniform diameter kept in chilled water in the irradiation chamber of Gamma Cell 220. The dose rate was 1.50 Gy/min as determined by FBX dosimetry²⁶. Purity of H₁ histone and DNA were checked by gel electrophoresis²⁷ and $A_{260\text{ nm}}/A_{280\text{ nm}}$ ²⁸. Analytical measurements with the experimental solutions were done by the instruments mentioned earlier in the unirradiated and gamma irradiated states.

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